

**SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND PERCEPTION OF COLLEGE
YOUTH: A STUDY OF MUMBAI WESTERN REGION**

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Abstract:

Social Entrepreneurship and Social Entrepreneurs has gained attention over the last decade and more. Social entrepreneurship is the act of taking ahead an innovative idea to address the issues present in society. There are many examples which show the visible impact of social entrepreneurship in changing the society. Over the period of time the concept, impact and belief of social entrepreneurship has been changed. Young and successful social entrepreneurs have motivated the youth to take the social cause and address along with economic benefit for the society especially underprivileged section. The research paper collected the data by using primary data analysis of 57 respondents. The questions related to social entrepreneurship has been asked to understand the perception of college youth towards the concept of social entrepreneurship.

Key word: *Entrepreneurship, Social Entrepreneurship, Social Issues, Youth*

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Introduction:

“A little bit of good can turn into a whole lot of good when fuelled by the commitment of a social entrepreneur.” This quote is given by Jeff Skoll, the Founder of Skull World Forum. Entrepreneurs are the generator of employment and backbone of economy. Entrepreneurs seek an opportunity to create something new and this afford is having motive of economic benefit. Whereas, social entrepreneur pursue an opportunity to address a social issue along with economic benefit at minimal level. The aim of social entrepreneurs is to bring

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transformation in social problem and make life of society better. The person who take up the social cause and develop solution for it is known as Social entrepreneur. The birth of social entrepreneurship was not profit centred initially but the effort of social entrepreneur for development of social and economic development along with profit create capital for continuing the work and less depended on outside resources such as government aid, investors etc.

The social entrepreneurs are self -motivated to create difference in life of people especially to the under-privileged section of society. In past few years there has been increased in number of young social entrepreneurs who are addressing the social and environmental issues with innovative ideas. There are many successful social entrepreneurs at global level and at domestic level. The courage to take up the cause and the action of young entrepreneur make them social entrepreneur. India having a huge population size of youth, and there are many young social entrepreneurs. Social entrepreneurs are different from N.G.O, N.P.O. as the social entrepreneurs create resource through their activity. Social entrepreneurs take the principles of entrepreneurship and try to create social change.

The youth are the active participant in nation building. As per Census 2011 the youth population in India is 28% of the total population and the expected increase has been expected upto 34% of total population in 2020. The age range of youth for the population between age of 17 years to 24 years as per national youth policy 2014. The action and activities of youth of society gives shape to society and future prospects. The youth of any country are having amazing power to change and develop the country. The participation of youth are required in prosperity, development of any society.

Types of Social entrepreneurship:

- Community project
- Non-profit Organisation & Non -Government Organisation
- Social Enterprises
- Social Purpose Business

Characteristics of social entrepreneurs:

- Self-Motivated
- Involve in capacity building process

- Aim of creating social value
- Courage to take up challenges related to social issue and finding solution
- Becoming resourceful to society.
- Helps in resource mobilisation

1.3 Some of the Top Social Entrepreneurs in India:

Social entrepreneurs are those entrepreneurs who are exploratory in nature and take up the step to address the social issues and find solution for it in positive way without taking help of any fund from government. The work of these social entrepreneurs create example in society and motivate others to be social entrepreneur. And when there are examples of young social entrepreneurs it motivate more young population to be part of journey of social entrepreneur.

1. **Jeroo Bilimoria-** She is founder of many NGOs. She has initiated the children programme which has been started to help the healthcare and police assistance to the children mainly to the abandoned children. She has also worked in area of self-empowerment of women through employment.
2. **Ria Sharma-** She is founder of Make love No Scare, a N.G.O. for rehabilitation of acid attack survivors. It is a crowd funding organisation for the help of acid attack survivors.
3. **Sunil Bharati Mittal-** He has initiate low cost mobile phone to support the farmers who can get updates of weathers and crops. Also he is founder of N.G.O. which gives free education and entrepreneurship training to the underprivileged youths.
4. **Hanumappa Sudarshan-** He is founder of Karuna Trust. This trust is working for the rights and up liftment of tribal population.
5. **Ajaita Shah-** She is the founder of Frontier market. The motive of this company is to make access of quality consumer durable product to the low income group people.
6. **Shaheen Mistry-** She is founder of Akanksha Foundation. The foundation has been set up to give education to the children of underprivileged section of society.
7. **Sushmita Ghose-** She is founder of Change maker an online platform to solve the open source problem.
8. **Sharad Vivek Sagar-** He is founder of Dexterity Global. This N.G.O. has been initiated to connect children from remotest areas with the best opportunities for them.

9. **Agnishwar Jayprakash-** He is founder of Ignite-India. The aim of this N.G.O is to provide a nationwide platform for students to promote innovation and entrepreneurship in high schools and colleges. It is recognised as best socio-economic educational movement by United Nation.
10. **Aarushi Batra-** She is founder of Robin Hood Army. This N.G.O. is set up to provide the surplus foods of various restaurants and weddings to the needy people.

Objectives

1. To study the basic framework of social entrepreneurship.
2. To study the characteristic of social entrepreneurs.
3. To study the perception of youth regarding social entrepreneurship

Review of Literature:

Young Social Entrepreneurs in Canada (2003) there is thin line between social entrepreneurship and social non-profit activity. The social entrepreneurship is a hybrid method of entrepreneurship and social responsibilities. The approach of social entrepreneurship is addressing the social issues which are from long period and some- time very complex in nature.

Rawal Tripda (2018) the impact of social entrepreneurship is seen on society at large. The basic characteristic of social entrepreneurship is same as entrepreneurship. The difference is in the objective of making the profit. In India the social entrepreneurship is having good prospects. The support from government and other stakeholders are required to make the social entrepreneurs successful and addressing the social issues.

Gandhi Tanvi & Raina Rishabh (2018) the concept of social entrepreneurship has become popular over a period of time. Recognition of idea to solve the social issue is the first step in social entrepreneurship. There is increase in number of educational institution who are offering training in area of social entrepreneurship.

Agafonow Alejandro (2014) the presence of non -profit organisation and non -governmental organisations address the social issues but do not create any economic value. The non -profit organisation and non -governmental organisations utilise the funds from government. Social entrepreneurship is the way of value creation while addressing the social issues and also focusing on economic prospects.

Sharma Anita (2014) the role of educational institutions and governments is very important to motivate the young to enter in area of social entrepreneurship as a career choice. The provisions of financial supports, setting up of incubation centres, certificate programs will reduce the fear of loss or failure among the youth in process of taking social entrepreneurship as career option.

4. Data Analysis & Interpretation:

For the present study the responses of 57 respondents has been recorded. The respondents are college youth of Mumbai Western Region. The response has been collected through primary data and the objective of collecting the responses to find out the perception of college youth regarding social entrepreneurship. The collected data is presented in the following tables.

Table 4.1			
Gender of Respondents			
Sr. No	Response	No. Of Response	Percentages
1	Male	38	66.67
2	Female	16	28.07
3	Prefer not to say	3	5.26
	Total	57	100

Interpretation:

The above table 4.1 no. shows that there are 66.67 percentages male respondents and 28.07 percentages respondent are female. There are 5.26 percentages of respondents who are not willing to disclose the gender.

Table 4.2			
Age Of Respondents			
Sr. No	Response	No. Of Response	Percentages
1	17 years to 19 years	3	5.3
2	20 years to 22 years	48	84.2
3	23 years to 24 years	6	10.5
	Total	57	100

Interpretation:

The above table no. 4.2 represents the age classification of the respondents. There are 84.2 percentages of respondents who are of age between 20 years to 22 years, followed by 10.5 percentages of respondents who are of age between 23 years to 24 years. And 5.3 percentages

of respondents are of age between 17 years to 19 years.

Table 4.3			
Educational level Of Respondents			
Sr. No	Response	No. Of Response	Percentages
1	Students of Undergraduate course	54	94.7
2	Students of post- graduation course	3	5.3
		57	100

Interpretation:

Table no. 4.3 shows the educational level of respondents. The respondents are college youth 94.7 percentages of respondents are student of undergraduate level course and 5.3 percentages of respondents are students of post -graduation courses.

Table 4.4			
Awareness among Respondents regarding Social Entrepreneurship			
Sr. No	Response	No. Of Response	Percentages
1	Yes	42	73.7
2	No	15	26.3
	Total	57	100

Interpretation:

The above table no. 4.4 shows the awareness among the youth regarding concept of social entrepreneurship. There are 73.7 percentages of respondents are aware about the concept of social entrepreneurship and 26.3 percentages of respondents are not aware about the concept of social entrepreneurship.

Table 4.5			
Source of Information regarding Social Entrepreneurship			
Sr. No.	Response	No. Of Response	Percentages
1	Friends	9	23.1
2	Conference /Seminars	4	0.85
3	Mentor/Teacher	3	7.6
4	Social Media platform	26	69.2
	Total	42	100

Interpretation:

The above table no. 4.5 shows the source of information regarding the concept of social entrepreneurship. Among the respondents there are 69.2 percentages of respondents who

come to know about social entrepreneurship through social media platform followed by 23.1 percentages of respondents. There are 7.6 percentages of respondents who got the information through their teachers and mentors, 0.85 percentages of respondents has attended conference and seminar and come to know about social entrepreneurship.

Awareness About any Social Entrepreneur			
Sr. No	Response	No. Of Response	Percentages
1	Yes	30	52.6
2	No	27	47.4
	Total	57	100

Interpretation:

Table no. 4.6 shows the awareness among respondents regarding the social entrepreneurs. Among the total respondents 52.6 percentages of respondents are aware about the social entrepreneurs and 47.4 percentages of respondents are not aware about any social entrepreneur.

Inclusion of Social Entrepreneurship in Curriculum			
Sr. No	Response	No. Of Response	Percentages
1	Yes	28	49.12
2	No	3	5.26
3	May be	26	45.62
	Total	57	100

Interpretation:

The above table no.4.7 shows the opinion of respondents towards inclusion of Social Entrepreneurship in curriculum. There are 49.12 percentages of respondents who are in opinion of inclusion of the concept of social entrepreneurship curriculum followed by 45.62 percentage of respondents who are not sure regarding the inclusion of the concept of social entrepreneurship curriculum and 5.26 percentages of respondents are not in opinion of inclusion of the concept of social entrepreneurship curriculum.

Choosing Social Entrepreneurship as career option			
Sr. No	Response	No. Of Response	Percentages
1	Yes	27	47.36
2	No	2	5.3
3	May be	28	49.6
	Total	57	100

Interpretation:

The above table no 4.8 shows the interest of the respondents towards taking social entrepreneurship as career option. There are 47.36 percentages of respondents who are ready to take up social entrepreneurship as career option followed by 49.6 percentages of respondents are not sure to take up social entrepreneurship as career option and only 5.3 percentages of respondents are not ready to take up social entrepreneurship as career option.

Conclusion:

Dees J. G. (2007) social entrepreneurship is the outcome of the innovation and creative thinking of leaders. The aim of social entrepreneurship is to encourage the society towards taking up the social and environmental goals. The youth are motivated and are in position to be leader with innovative ideas to address the social and environmental issues. The study has as shown that the youth are aware about the social entrepreneurship and they are motivated to take the social cause and deal with it in economic ways. The youth are in opinion to include the social entrepreneurship in curriculum so that more and more youth can be aware with the importance of it. The youth are having doubt to adopt the social entrepreneurship as career due to the absence of required information and the challenges faced by them in this context. The support for government to the social entrepreneurs will motivate more and more youth to come ahead and address the social issues with economic benefits of all stakeholders.

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